

Subject – subject interaction as a pedagogical condition for developing the legal culture of future managers

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Annotation. The article substantiates subject–subject interaction as an essential pedagogical condition for developing the legal culture of future managers in the process of professional training. It emphasizes that legal culture constitutes an integral component of managerial competence, as it ensures the ability to act in accordance with legislation, adhere to ethical norms, and make well-grounded managerial decisions. Based on an analysis of scholarly discourse, the study identifies approaches to understanding the essence of legal culture and the pedagogical conditions that contribute to its development. Particular attention is given to the role of subject–subject interaction as a mechanism for activating students’ value-motivational sphere, fostering responsibility, lawful behavior, and professional self-determination.

The content of the pedagogical condition— the use of subject–subject interaction aimed at stimulating the development of legal culture among future managers —is examined as a means of ensuring positive learning motivation, awareness of the significance of legal knowledge, and readiness to apply it in managerial practice. The article analyzes the potential of interactive teaching methods, namely, interactive and problem-based lectures, workshop seminars that promote the development of legal consciousness, acquisition of experience in lawful behavior, and formation of value-based attitudes toward professional activity. It is demonstrated that the implementation of subject–subject interaction enhances the effectiveness of the educational process, as it creates conditions for the development of independence, accountability, critical thinking, reflection, and partnership relations between teachers and students.

The study concludes that the systematic application of pedagogical conditions grounded in subject–subject interaction ensures the comprehensive formation of the legal culture of future managers and improves the quality of their professional training in higher education institutions.

Keywords: subject–subject interaction, pedagogical condition, legal culture, future managers, professional training, higher education, pedagogical stimulation, interactive teaching methods.

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Суб'єкт-суб'єктна взаємодія як педагогічна умова формування правової культури майбутніх менеджерів

Анотація. У статті обґрунтовано суб'єкт-суб'єктну взаємодію як важливу педагогічну умову формування правової культури майбутніх менеджерів у процесі професійної підготовки. Акцентовано, що правова культура є складовою професійної компетентності управлінця, оскільки забезпечує здатність діяти відповідно до законодавства, дотримуватися етичних норм та ухвалювати обґрунтовані управлінські рішення. На основі аналізу науково-педагогічних джерел визначено підходи до розуміння сутності правової культури та педагогічних умов, що сприяють її розвитку. Особливу увагу приділено ролі суб'єкт-суб'єктної взаємодії як механізму активізації ціннісно-мотиваційної сфери студентів, формування їхньої відповідальності, здатності до правомірної поведінки та професійного самовизначення.

Розглянуто зміст педагогічної умови – використання суб'єкт-суб'єктної взаємодії з метою стимулювання формування правової культури майбутніх менеджерів, що забезпечує позитивну навчальну мотивацію, усвідомлення значущості правових знань та готовність студентів до їх застосування в управлінській діяльності. Проаналізовано можливості інтерактивних методів навчання, зокрема інтерактивної, проблемної лекцій та семінару-практикуму, що сприяють розвитку правосвідомості, набуттю досвіду правомірної поведінки та формуванню ціннісного ставлення до управлінської практики. Доведено, що впровадження суб'єкт-суб'єктної взаємодії підсилює ефективність освітнього процесу, оскільки створює умови для розвитку самостійності, відповідальності за результати, критичного мислення, рефлексії та партнерських відносин між викладачем і студентами.

Зроблено висновок, що системне застосування суб'єкт-суб'єктної взаємодії в освітньому процесі забезпечує цілісне формування правової культури майбутніх менеджерів та підвищує якість їхньої професійної підготовки у закладах вищої освіти.

Ключові слова: суб'єкт-суб'єктна взаємодія, педагогічна умова, правова культура, майбутні менеджери, професійна підготовка, вища освіта, педагогічне стимулювання, інтерактивні методи навчання.

Introduction

Legal culture is an integral component of the professional development of a modern specialist, since it determines their level of legal awareness, responsibility, and ability to act within the framework of current legislation. It encompasses not only knowledge of legal norms but also the ability to apply them in real-life contexts, adhere to ethical principles, and build relationships based on respect for the rights and freedoms of others. These aspects make legal culture a fundamental prerequisite for successful professional activity in any field.

In the system of higher education, the formation of legal culture among future managers becomes particularly important, as this group of professionals will make managerial decisions that influence organizational processes, business communication, and compliance with legal requirements. The professional training of managers involves developing not only professional competencies but also legal awareness, which helps ensure transparency, responsibility, and fairness in their future professional practice. Therefore, the educational process should be aimed at fostering readiness to act lawfully, ethically, and professionally in a dynamic modern environment.

In this context, there is a need for pedagogical conditions that promote not only the transfer of legal knowledge but also the development of an active legal position and responsible attitude toward future professional activity. One of the key conditions that ensures deep assimilation of legal information and the development of value orientations is subject-subject interaction in the educational process, which serves not only as a methodological foundation of modern instruction but also as an effective mechanism for shaping legal awareness and

responsible behavior among future managers, in line with the current demands of their professional training.

An analysis of scientific and pedagogical literature indicates a significant scholarly interest in exploring pedagogical conditions necessary for the successful professional development of future managers. In particular, this issue has been addressed in the works of such researchers as Budianska and Zakharova, Demchenko, Dzekun and Chaban, Korolova, Kostyuchyk, Levadna, Litvinova, Nestulia, Poleshchuk, Romanovskiy and Chebotarov, Sarkisova, Sorokotiaga, Shapolova, Tasyts, Shevchuk, Vasylyshyna, Zhytomyrska and Slabko, and others.

The purpose of this article is to substantiate subject–subject interaction as an important pedagogical condition for stimulating the development of future managers’ legal culture and to identify its impact on the effectiveness of their professional training in higher education institutions.

Results

To ensure the effectiveness of developing the legal culture of future specialists in management, it is crucial to identify pedagogical conditions that facilitate the productive acquisition of knowledge on the legal aspects of managerial activity, the development of practical skills and competencies, and the cultivation of students’ value-based attitudes toward law and legal culture. In order to outline the pedagogical conditions that contribute to the formation of future managers’ legal culture within the context of university education, it is necessary to clarify the term “pedagogical condition,” taking into account diverse interpretations of this concept presented across scholarly discourse.

An analysis of scientific and pedagogical literature indicates a multiplicity in interpreting the concept of “pedagogical conditions,” since the effectiveness of forming future managers’ specific competencies largely depends on how this concept is understood and justified. Namely, the concept of “pedagogical condition” is defined as “a set of objective learning opportunities that ensure the successful solution of a given task” [13, p. 121]; “features of organizing the educational process that ensure the integrity of training and education of future specialists, contribute to their comprehensive development, and the formation of necessary qualities, skills, knowledge, and abilities” [17, p. 68]; “a set of factors that regulate and coordinate the interaction of objects and phenomena within the pedagogical process to achieve the intended goal, improve interpersonal relationships among participants, and facilitate the activation of students’ educational and cognitive activities, their independence, initiative, and professional interest” [4, p. 227]; and “factors that ensure the effective interaction of components of the pedagogical process to achieve the intended goal, enhance teacher–student relationships during learning to solve specific didactic tasks, and promote students’ educational activity, independence, initiative, professional interest, and the development of professional competencies” [10, p. 59].

In the dissertation devoted to the problem of preparing future managers for professional activity during university studies, Kobets defines pedagogical conditions as “a set of external and internal factors, processes, and phenomena of the educational environment, purposefully created and implemented by teachers, which influence the learning, development, and upbringing of students, as well as their dynamics and final outcomes” [8, p. 125]. The author emphasizes that, in the context of this study, the concept should be considered as a set of interrelated and mutually conditioned circumstances that facilitate the establishment of a purposeful process of preparing future managers for professional activity [8].

Addressing the issue of forming pedagogical conditions for developing organizational readiness for managerial activity, Vasylyshyna asserts that “the most significant factor in increasing the effectiveness of learning in higher education institutions is the creation of psycho-pedagogical conditions in which a student can take an active personal stance and fully develop as a subject of learning activity... Therefore, attention should be paid to the level and

content of student activity, determined by specific teaching methods: activity at the level of perception and understanding; imagination and creative thinking; reproduction activity; creation of something new; social activity” [3, p. 92]. In studying the problem of pedagogical interaction between instructors and future organizational managers in the process of professional training, Marchuk emphasizes that “it is necessary to create organizational and pedagogical conditions that ensure effective pedagogical interaction based on achieving a defined common educational goal through the use of modern learning technologies. Such conditions should also consider instructors’ readiness for innovative activity, in particular, the adaptation of communication styles between instructors and students to a student-centered approach” [11, p. 89].

Tasyts summarizes his understanding of the concept by suggesting the following definition: “Pedagogical conditions are the result of the purposeful selection, design, and application of content elements, methods, techniques, and organizational forms of learning to achieve didactic objectives” [17, p. 235]. Based on this interpretation, the scholar offers his own classification of pedagogical conditions, dividing them into “objective: persuasive motivation and clear goal-setting, rational planning, organization of control, objective evaluation; a favorable moral and psychological climate in the group; production, household, and sanitary-hygienic conditions in accordance with accepted standards; subjective: the presence of a pronounced need and stable motives for activity in the subject, acceptance of the goals and program of activity; experience in organizing and performing the activity: theoretical preparedness, developed skills and practical actions; correspondence of the content and nature of the activity to individual characteristics of the subject; emotional, psychological, and physical state of the subject” [17, p. 235].

Within the context of our study, and based on the analysis of contemporary scientific discourse, we define pedagogical conditions as a set of managed and interrelated factors in the educational process that are applied to ensure and enhance the effectiveness of professional training with the aim of forming a high level of legal culture among future managers at higher education institutions.

Considering our reflections on the concept of pedagogical conditions, the analysis of scientific and pedagogical sources, and the practical experience of professional training of future managers in the context of higher education, we identify the following pedagogical conditions for forming the legal culture of future specialists in the field of management within the Ukrainian higher education system: the use of subject–subject interaction to stimulate the development of legal culture among future managers; integration of the content of legal culture into the academic disciplines of the professional training cycle for future managers; activation of students’ learning activities through interaction to develop legal culture; improvement of scientific and methodological support for academic disciplines in the professional training cycle for future managers based on developed methodological recommendations.

The first pedagogical condition – the use of subject–subject interaction to stimulate the development of legal culture among future managers – serves as a foundation for the effective formation of legal culture among future managers. In the context of democratization, informatization, and dynamic development in all spheres of social life, higher education faces the need to seek modern approaches to professional training. Currently, there is a tendency to radically change the educational paradigm from subject–object interaction between participants, where the instructor is the primary source and provider of information while the student is a passive recipient, to subject–subject relations between instructors and students, based on equal pedagogical interaction during the process of acquiring knowledge, skills, and competencies. We support Andrushchenko’s assertion that “education is, first and foremost, a process of subject–subject interaction between the teacher (educator) and the student, aimed at the transmission of knowledge, formation of skills and competencies, and the cultivation of

a culture of thinking and the capacity for self-learning and independent creative activity” [1, p. 355].

In our view, the justification of this pedagogical condition for forming the legal culture of future specialists in management should appropriately begin with an interpretation of the concept of “subject–subject interaction.” Within the scientific discourse, this concept is interpreted as “a certain form of interactive cooperation between an instructor and a higher education student” [12, p. 4]; “interpersonal interaction of participants in the educational process, which fulfills the student’s basic need to engage with society and culture on the basis of equal partnership with the educator, and reflects readiness for mutual understanding and respect during communication and activity; a direct or mediated influence of subjects on each other that generates their mutual interdependence and connection” [2, p. 254]; and “an intrinsic characteristic and result of pedagogical interaction, organized in accordance with the patterns of the educational process, the conditions for implementing a learner-centered and activity-based approach, and the principles of forming subject–subject relations” [7, p. 224].

We consider that the successful implementation of subject–subject interaction between participants in the educational process depends on a clearly formulated goal, the selected forms, methods, and means of learning activities, as well as the intended learning outcomes. In particular, Tsyganchuk defines the principle of subject–subject interaction between an instructor and a student as aimed at “building equal and trusting relationships, implemented through mentorship programs, extracurricular activities, psychological support, and methods of personal, empathetic, and benevolent communication, thus fostering mutual understanding and student support by instructors” [16, p. 75]. As Yashchenko notes, the subject–subject approach to organizing the educational process “is directed not only at mastering a certain body of knowledge but also at the ways of acquiring it, thinking and activity, and at the development of students’ cognitive abilities and creative potential” [20, p. 532].

In the course of studying the theoretical foundations for establishing subject–subject relations between instructors and students, Yatsula emphasizes the fundamental role of communication, particularly in the form of dialogue among participants, which increases intrinsic motivation, generates interest in the subject matter, and stimulates collaboration and self-development. The scholar suggests that “such an approach is effective when engaging the value-semantic sphere of the individual. Dialogue, under these conditions, is understood as the value of creative self-development for its participants. In this process, the creative ‘self-concept’ of both the instructor and the student is realized” [19, p. 224].

Analyzing the essence of subject–subject interaction in education, Barbashova identifies key characteristics of this phenomenon: “personal orientation – the ability to understand the interlocutor; equality of psychological positions – the instructor should not dominate communication and must recognize the student’s right to their own opinion and position; activity of all participants, the ability to develop a joint strategy, consciously improve oneself; readiness to accept the feelings, experiences, and perspectives of others; use of non-standard forms of communication – moving beyond the purely role-based position of the instructor” [2, p. 254]. Additionally, Khomenko highlights conditions that enable effective subject–subject relations between instructors and students, namely: “value-based attitude toward the individual considering each student’s professional interests; dialogical nature of pedagogical communication; student engagement in various forms of research activity, which enhances the significance of the interactions; collaboration and co-creation in relationships; reliance on the participants’ level of culture and competence as a factor in personal development” [15, p. 69].

Therefore, applying the concept of “subject–subject interaction” to our research, we argue that such pedagogical relations between instructors and students in the field of management involve joint activity and interaction as equal participants in the educational process. This serves as a prerequisite for stimulating future managers to develop legal culture, enhance motivation to acquire new legal knowledge, skills, and competencies, and cultivate legal

awareness and value-based understanding of the role of law in managerial practice. We contend that the effectiveness of forming legal culture in future managers depends, on the one hand, on the students' active stance and intrinsic motivation toward legal self-improvement and conscious adherence to legal principles, and, on the other hand, on the instructor's partnership-oriented approach based on mutual respect and tolerance, readiness for collaboration, and the use of problem-based and interactive methods in organizing the educational process. This approach increases interest in the learning content and stimulates the professional development of future managerial specialists.

In studying effective means of stimulating students' learning activities in the context of university education, Volkova highlights the following: "creating an innovative and developmental educational environment in the process of professional training of future specialists; ensuring diversification of the university's educational services; reorienting the educational process toward the formation of professional competence and the competitiveness of future specialists" [6, pp. 162–163]. She further focuses attention on the fact that the implementation of these measures is possible through the continuous updating of curricula in accordance with students' professional needs and employers' requirements; the use of modern interactive, learner-centered, and information and communication technologies in organizing the educational process; provision of psychological and pedagogical support and individual assistance to each student during learning; and active engagement of students in research activities from the first year, as well as in various forms of practical and extracurricular activities, to realize professional initiatives in cooperation with university partners or potential employers [6].

From our perspective, the concept of "pedagogical stimulation" should be applied to our study—the formation of legal culture among future managers in higher education. We define it as a purposeful process of implementing systematic pedagogical influences on students in the field of management, aimed at activating their educational and cognitive activities in mastering legal knowledge, creating a productive environment for developing skills in its practical application through real managerial scenarios, raising awareness of the importance of law in professional activity, and enhancing motivation for self-development and self-realization as future successful specialists. Furthermore, pedagogical stimulation of future specialists in management contributes to the establishment of a law-conscious professional stance, which directly influences the formation of an internal attitude toward adherence to regulatory and corporate principles in managerial activity.

In this context, the stimulation of legal culture formation is viewed as an effective mechanism for activating legal knowledge, skills, and competencies, including legal analysis and application, legal awareness, legal thinking, and lawful behavior. This is achieved through the implementation of modern forms and methods of educational process organization, the democratization of interactions between participants, and the provision of feedback and opportunities for reflection.

The implementation of the pedagogical condition—using subject–subject interaction to stimulate the formation of legal culture among future managers — occurs in higher education through the use of interactive teaching methods designed to increase motivation to study law, actively involve students in practical application of acquired knowledge, and create a comfortable learning environment for effective interaction among participants. Contemporary researchers agree that interactive learning methods stimulate professional interest, enhance effective knowledge acquisition, model professional behavior, increase motivation, strengthen knowledge retention, foster teamwork, and provide freedom for self-expression, thereby supporting the holistic formation of future specialists' professional competencies.

Within our study, we highlight interactive lectures, which combine theoretical content delivery with practical components for developing legal culture among future managers. Problem-based lectures in the professional training of students majoring in management

activate analytical and critical thinking, and the ability to independently seek professional solutions aligned with the principles of legality and corporate ethics. Among interactive learning tools, the case method plays a leading role, offering students the opportunity to analyze real managerial situations, enhance skills in legal reasoning and the analysis of normative and legal documents, and demonstrate the inseparable link between theoretical knowledge and practical application. Simulation methods allow modeling of real-life professional scenarios, in which future managers work under conditions closely approximating reality, developing business communication skills, teamwork, responsibility, and awareness of the consequences of their actions.

It is worth noting that an interactive lecture combines traditional lectures with interactive teaching technologies such as video presentations, group interaction, and various educational games. This approach creates a favorable learning atmosphere in which students actively participate, express opinions, ask questions, and receive feedback. This, in turn, enhances motivation, stimulates interest in the learning content, and ensures successful knowledge acquisition. As Shkola and Saliuk [18, p. 437] state, “interactivity involves dialogical engagement, consideration of each problem from multiple perspectives, rejection of rigid templates (multiplicity of logic), the shift of traditional instructor activity to student activity, and the direction of students toward independent information search, knowledge exchange, and interaction within groups, subgroups, and pairs.” This lecture format is based on student-centered and multimodal learning approaches, which involve active student participation using modern teaching methods. Interactive lectures facilitate understanding and assimilation of theoretical concepts, while enhancing teamwork and critical thinking skills.

In contemporary higher education institutions involved in the professional training of future managers, the case method has become widely used. This method involves the analysis of real legal situations that require students to apply theoretical knowledge to solve practical tasks. This approach promotes the development of critical thinking, analytical skills, and practical legal competencies. The case method is an effective way to develop the ability to analyze and evaluate professional scenarios, followed by problem-solving during group discussions. Teamwork allows for productive engagement with the learning material, development of critical analysis skills, situational interpretation, decision-making, and drawing conclusions using both inductive and deductive reasoning. This teaching method encourages reflection, discussion with instructors, and participation in group dialogues, thereby stimulating professional interest, motivating self-directed learning, and supporting professional self-determination [21]

In the context of our study, the case method enables management students to acquire skills in analyzing legal sources, applying current legislation to real managerial situations, justifying their positions based on legal and ethical principles, and selecting lawful approaches to professional problem-solving. Moreover, future managers develop effective communication and collaboration skills in professional environments, which helps them form an accurate understanding of professional models of lawful behavior inherent in management practice.

The organization of an interactive lecture also involved a role-playing game using the simulation method, which is based on an activity-based approach to the educational process, immersing students in scenarios closely approximating real professional situations. Korolyuk and Kononets emphasize that effective simulation involves three structural components: “a well-designed model of the professional environment offering key behavior and interaction options; a simulation scenario aimed at developing intuition and exploring alternative solutions to problems; and a mentor who employs the scaffolding strategy, characterized by gradually decreasing support from the instructor as students work independently” [9, p. 166].

We argue that the use of simulation in organizing role-playing games for management students is one of the most effective ways to familiarize them with the realities of their future profession. Participants assume defined roles and must make strategic decisions based on their

professional knowledge, legal frameworks, and ethical codes. This method promotes active student engagement in the classroom, better assimilation of theoretical management concepts, increased motivation and enthusiasm for collaborative problem-solving, improvement of public speaking skills, and enhanced emotional engagement when facing realistic workplace challenges [22]

A problem-based lecture is a form of organizing the educational process that promotes knowledge acquisition through problem questions, situations, or tasks. Its primary goal is to provide students with opportunities to gain knowledge through active thinking, discussion, and independent initiative in problem-solving. The instructor's task is to clearly outline the problem by posing a controversial question to stimulate independent inquiry and formulation of conclusions. Consequently, the learning process becomes problem-oriented and "encourages students to think independently, develops their abilities for analysis, synthesis, comparison, generalization, and creative problem-solving" [5, p. 314].

Among the effective forms of professional training for future managers are practical seminars, which foster legal culture by combining theoretical knowledge with practical skills through the resolution of real professional tasks. During the seminar-practical, alongside academic knowledge, special attention should be given to developing a deep understanding of legal principles, the importance of legality and law and order, as well as critical thinking skills and responsible attitudes toward one's rights and duties.

Practical seminars enable future managers not only to consolidate legal knowledge and ethical principles but also to apply them in practice through discussion, case analysis, and role-playing. This form of instruction enhances skills in making reasoned and lawful decisions, analyzing situations from multiple perspectives, improving business communication, fostering responsibility for adherence to corporate and legal standards and professional ethics, and developing high levels of legal competence, culture, and awareness.

Conclusions

Thus, the effectiveness of implementing the pedagogical condition of using subject-subject interaction to stimulate the development of legal culture among future managers is analyzed in terms of developing the axiological component of future managers' legal culture. This development is manifested not only in their awareness of the value foundations of professional activity but also in the formation of a stable system of professional and ethical priorities that guide their decision-making in complex organizational contexts. It reflects their intrinsic motivation to acquire and deepen legal knowledge, as well as their readiness to apply it thoughtfully and responsibly in professional settings, in accordance with current legislation and the moral and ethical principles of managerial practice. Moreover, it contributes to the formation of critical thinking, ethical judgment, and a proactive approach to professional accountability, thereby enhancing the overall quality of managerial activities. By fostering these competencies, the pedagogical condition creates a solid foundation for future managers to navigate the dynamic and ethically challenging realities of modern professional environments with confidence and responsibility.

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